

Best practice guide on the conduction of life cycle tests and correlated measurement of Li-ion battery cell impedances

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1 Scope

Impedance measurements and, i.e. electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), of Li-ion batteries are very sensitive to a variety of measurement conditions. The results can hardly be reproduced and are subject to misinterpretation if the measurement parameters are ill-defined. This fundamental issue, that is often not adequately addressed, applies particularly to its use in life cycle tests (LCT). Impedance results of LCTs are correlated in one or the other way with the aging of the battery under investigation. Thus, it is of crucial importance to define adequate reproducibility conditions for impedance measurements and LCTs. Well defined measurement conditions will guarantee their metrological comparability, will provide stable results and will avoid misinterpretation of LCT observations.

This best practice guide addresses parameters that must be considered and proposes steps and tests to be conducted before a LCT to specify them. Measurement conditions often depend on the objective of the LCT. Therefore, it might be necessary to adapt the definition and determination of the parameters proposed in this best practice guide to the specific requirements of an LCT. However, this best practice guide will nevertheless help to increase the sensitivity of the user for the demands of low-impedance Li-ion battery cell measurements and it will provide guidance on how adequate reproducibility conditions can be established for a specific measurement task.

This best practice guide addresses LCTs of Li-ion battery cells specifically. It summarizes the definitions and methodologies used in the LiBforSecUse project to establish reproducibility conditions for interlaboratory collaboration. In this project, mainly NMC based cathode chemistry has been used. The guide is intended to be a concise document for practical step by step use rather than being a comprehensive discussion paper of various alternative methods, even though further background is included to some extent. It might also be used for other battery cell types, modules and packs. In this case, additional parameters might be considered, such as the balancing of each cell charge and discharge in modules for instance.

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2 Definition of operation parameters

Some battery related terms can be defined in different ways. The state-of-charge (SoC) can be defined in terms of the open-source-voltage or the discharge (or charge) current with respect to the total capacity. The latter can be defined in terms of the nominal capacity, the capacity at the beginning of life or the actually remaining capacity. Moreover, the measured capacity depends on measurement temperature and current. Obviously, the definition may strongly affect the quantity value of the SoC. Therefore, clear definitions of the quantities relevant for the measurements are crucial. In this guide, the following definitions are used

U_{\max}	Upper voltage limit of the cell, as specified by the manufacturer. NOTE: U_{\max} is usually the upper cut-off voltage for capacity measurements and cycling.
U_{\min}	Lower voltage limit of the cell, as specified by the manufacturer.
U_{cut}	Lower cut-off voltage for cycling and capacity measurements.
Charge of a cell	$C(t) = 1 - \int_0^t i(t') dt'$, whereas the lower integration boundary $t=0$ refers to a fully charged cell and $i(t)$ is the discharge current. Note1: The charge of a cell (and the corresponding state of charge, SoC) is defined in terms of a discharge current for practical reasons. In practice, a cell is fully charged to define a clear reference for SoC adjustment. Note2: Discharge is considered to be interrupted if the cell voltage reaches U_{cut} , i.e. $i(t)$ becomes 0.
Capacity	Charge $C(t)$ at U_{cut} at a defined, constant discharge current and at a defined ambient temperature.
C_{nom}	Nominal capacity, capacity stated by the manufacturer
C_{max}	Actually available capacity at the discharge current and ambient temperature defined for the capacity measurement, NOTE: C_{max} decreases over time
CC	Constant current
CV	Constant voltage
C-rate	Current scale specifically used in battery technology. 1 C is defined as the current needed to completely discharge a completely charged cell in 1 h; it is related to C_{max} in this document, if not mentioned otherwise
SoC	State of charge. In this document, it is defined as $C(t)/C_{\text{max}}$, given in %, and related to the discharge current and ambient temperature used to measure C_{max} . NOTE1: Consequently, SoC must be adjusted with the discharge current and at the ambient temperature used for C_{max} measurement.
SoH	State of health: C_{max} divided by the nominal capacity, given in % NOTE1: If the nominal capacity is not available, SoH is referred to the initially measured capacity. NOTE2: If $U_{\min} \neq U_{\text{cut}}$, SoH is referred to the initially measured capacity.
Fully charged cell	Defined by a charging current that drops below $C_{\text{nom}}/10$ at constant charging voltage U_{\max} (CV mode).
SoC100	State of charge of a fully charged cell.

Fully discharged cell	Defined by a cell voltage that is equal to U_{cut} or lower.
SoCO	SoC of a fully discharged cell at U_{cut} . NOTE: SoC100 is 100 % per definition, irrespective of the actual charge/discharge current and ambient temperature. Consequently, $C(t)$ and SoCO, respectively, may not be zero at U_{cut} , since the capacity depends on discharge current and ambient temperature. SoCO is only 0% if the cell has been completely discharged with the discharge current and ambient temperature used for C_{max} measurement.
Cell voltage	Voltage between the electric poles of a cell.
DoD	Depth of Discharge given in % Note: It is noted that DoD is not SoC in discharge but is associated to the difference of SoCs in an LCT, .e.g, DoD = 50 % can be associated to SoC = 100 % and SoC = 50 % or, likewise, SoC = 75 % and SoC = 25 %.
OCV	Open circuit voltage, cell voltage at zero current
qOCV	Quasi open circuit voltage, cell voltage at small currents which affect temperature and overpotentials of the cell minimally.
Full cycle (FC)	CC discharging of a previously fully charged cell (SoC100) at a defined current to SoCO, afterwards CC charging until the cell voltage reaches U_{max} , finally, CV charging to SoC100.
Refresh	If not mentioned otherwise: 1 FC at 1 C
Cell storage	Storage conditions: SOC=50 % and room temperature (20 °C to 25°C)
f_{min}	Minimal measurement frequency.
f_{max}	Maximal measurement frequency.
t_{meas}	Specified measurement temperature for impedance measurements, usually a temperature between 20 °C and 25 °C, often 23 °C is chosen.
Relaxation time t_R	Time elapsed until the cell is in an acceptable equilibrium state after last operation.
Equilibrium time t_e	Time elapsed until the cell temperature is in equilibrium with the ambient temperature (in the test chamber) after the ambient temperature has been changed to a new set value
EIS	Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy
LCT	Life cycle test

Other definitions might be more appropriate for specific investigations. For instance, it might be more useful to define $C_{max}=C_{nom}$ and SoC or DoD in terms of the cell voltage between the upper and lower voltage limits. This is often done to simplify the measurements. However, these simplifications also increase measurement uncertainty. Moreover, it must be emphasised that the subsequent guidelines are fundamentally based on the above definitions. Thus, the measurement steps must be adapted appropriately if definitions deviate from them.

3 Preparatory work

3.1 Identification of the Unit under test (UUT)

A unique identifier must be assigned to each cell.

Manufacturer specification must be sifted. All information characterising the cell must be noted, especially those relevant for safe operation

- manufacturer
- type number given by the manufacturer
- chemistry
- housing
- nominal capacity
- limiting voltages and currents
- range of ambient temperature for operation and storage
- other as stated by manufacturer

Initial tests should be performed, and the results should be noted

- visual inspection
- weight
- OCV at arrival

3.2 Definition of LCT parameters

Relevant LCT parameters must be identified and listed according to the objective of the investigation. Most relevant parameters are:

- C-rate for cycling
- cycling temperature(s)
- cycling pattern (CC-, CV-, recess-steps, EV-drive patterns, etc.)
- cut-off voltages for cycling
- interval of intermediate measurements (usually in terms of full cycles)
- kind of intermediate measurements (impedances at specific frequencies, EIS, internal resistance, capacity, etc.)
- compression of cell, if applicable
- torque of contact screws or contact pressure, if applicable
- torque moment for contact screws, if applicable

Other parameters might be relevant for specific objectives.

Some of the parameters might already be quantified at this stage. Others might require preliminary measurements (see below).

Cell data and defined LCT measurement parameters should be added to an LCT data sheet or data base.

3.3 Connection of a UUT

Realising reproducible low-impedance measurements is a challenging task regarding correct wiring, the calibration of an impedance measurement device, and subsequent correction of measurement errors. Therefore, these aspects are addressed by a stand-alone best practice guide¹. However, some important issues are summarised in this and the next section.

A simplified scheme of a typical connection is shown in Figure 1. In electrochemistry, the EIS meter (or RLC bridge) is typically equipped with a cable assembly (or multiple of assemblies).

Figure 1 Typical wiring scheme for the unit under test (UUT) and the impedance measurement device, e.g. for electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS).

Concerning low AC impedance measurements, the main source of errors is related to parasitic magnetic couplings between measurement leads, the UUT and shields. The effect increases with decreasing impedance and increasing frequency. The current flowing through the current circuitry induces parasitic voltage into voltage leads proportional to an effective mutual inductance M between the potential and current leads. It will appear as an offset X_{bias} on the reactance measurement, which is proportional to the angular frequency ω ($X_{\text{bias}} = \omega M$). In impedance metrology, this problem is suppressed by using so called four terminal pair connection (4TP), where all four leads are coaxial cables. An impedance meter designed for 4TP measurements imposes an opposite current flow via the shields to eliminate magnetic fields, so that coupling into the voltage leads is minimized. Calibration standards are almost exclusively realized in 4TP connection in low impedance metrology.

Some impedance (spectro-) meters are however not designed for 4TP configuration, but just for 4 terminal (4T) use, meaning there is no counter current imposed on the shields or there are no shields at all. In any case, it is most often necessary to traverse from four to two terminals, e.g. the battery terminals. The user will face the problem of mutual couplings at least in the test leads portion of interconnection as shown in Figure 1. The value of the parasitic reactance is hard to quantify as it will depend on the cable assembly. Some impedance meters may compensate it numerically for a specific cable assembly. However, others may not, and it is the user's responsibility to take this offset into account. The magnitude of the parasitic effect can be practically evaluated and minimized by rearranging the leads relative positions, twisting them, placing them to different mutual angles or so, and observing the changes in measured impedance.

Another problem is related to skin/proximity effects in the lead-joints and angular error, both affecting the real and imaginary part of the impedance measurements. They are usually compensated by so called SHORT correction (see below).

In any case, using proper geometry of interconnection is the best practice to minimize impedance bias. Fundamentally, the lead wires should be as short as possible. Secondly, current leads should be

¹ 10.5281/zenodo.5959781

twisted. Likewise, potential leads should be twisted. The two bundles should be kept as far apart as possible. Finally, mutual coupling is minimized if the two bundles are kept perpendicular. Often, multiple UUTs are measured simultaneously in the same test chamber. The cables might also affect each other by magnetic coupling. Therefore, the (shielded) cables of the UUTs should be kept apart from each other as good as possible.

It is most relevant how the UUT is connected to the test leads. 4-wire connection is indispensable. A good connection of the UUT is shown in Figure 2. There, the current and potential terminals of the UUT are coaxial and isolated (left). Often, the terminals are screws (e.g. prismatic cells) as shown on the right hand-side of Figure 2. It must be generally avoided that the measurement current flows via the connectors used for potential sensing because voltage drop on them would appear as offset in the impedance measurement. Finally, Figure 3 shows how to connect the wires of an additional cycling unit used for an LCT. Note that sometimes the cycling unit and the measuring unit share the same wires.

Figure 2 Connecting the four lead wires to the UUT (left), connecting potential and current wires to a pin tread (right). Always make sure the current is not lead across the contacts for measuring the potential.

Figure 3 Connecting impedance measurement leads and cycling wires to one terminal.

3.4 Calibration of impedance meters

3.4.1 SHORT correction

The basic idea is to measure the impedance bias of the parasitic effective series impedance of the whole connection assembly by measuring a short circuit and subtract the offset (short) impedance from a subsequent impedance measurement of the UUT. Practical realisation is however difficult. It must be expected that mutual coupling of a SHORT measurement is different compared to that of the subsequent UUT measurement, if connection and positioning of the lead wires are different. Thus, there remains an uncertainty in the SHORT correction. Nevertheless, the correction will reduce impedance measurement error. The only countermeasure in the typical 4T arrangement is to thoroughly consider the above-mentioned connection rules. It is also recommended to use a well characterised SHORT, so that the impedance value of the SHORT, Z_{SHORT_char} , can also be considered. If such a SHORT is not available, the lead wires should be short-circuited as shown in Figure 4. In particular, the current leads and the voltage leads must each be connected together as shown in Figure 4. The order of leads is critical. They must be connected so the current between the Hcur-Lcur leads is not inducing voltage to Hpot-Lpot loop.

Figure 4 Realisation of a short circuit in 4T topology.

It is recommended to measure the impedance of the SHORT, Z_{SHORT_meas} , at the same measurement frequencies as intended for the subsequent UUT measurement. Interpolation is not always usable if an EIS meter has its own frequency dependent offsets. Averaging should be sufficient to reduce noise to the desired level. Internal SHORT correction of the impedance meter can be used, but its repeatability may not be sufficient. Impedances of a subsequent measurement of a UUT, Z_{UUT_meas} , can easily be corrected subtracting the impedance Z_{SHORT_meas} of the SHORT measurement:

$$Z_{UUT_corr} = Z_{UUT_meas} - (Z_{SHORT_meas} - Z_{SHORT_char})$$

SHORT correction should be applied to any low-impedance measurement since it reduces the most significant uncertainty contribution. Note that Z_{SHORT_char} must be set to zero, if a characterised SHORT is not available. However, an adequate uncertainty should be assigned. A bad example of SHORT connection is shown in Figure 5. The twisted part of the leads will have an inductance variation of ± 5 nH per 10 cm in worst case. That is below ± 0.15 m Ω at 5 kHz. However, even the small non-twisted part of the leads shown in the example will induce uncertainty of some ± 50 nH, that is ± 1.5 m Ω at 5 kHz. Fortunately, the mutual coupling drops fast when the leads (bundles) are at least a few centimetres apart. The uncertainty of the real component in this arrangement will be up to few microohms. Note that another important source of uncertainty is the noise in the impedance measurement of the SHORT.

Figure 5 Example of parasitic mutual coupling of 4-wire connection.

3.5 Calibration with a reference impedance standard

SHORT correction can be used to reduce the measurement error related to cable assembly. It is likely, it will stay more or less constant in time unless the geometry of the leads is changed. However, an additional impedance error may occur that depends on the magnitude of the impedance to be measured. Such an error results from the measurement device rather than the UUT and the measurement setup. A characterised reference impedance standard, the impedance of which is similar to that of the UUT, can be used to measure the gain error (deviation of measured modulus $|Z|$) and phase error (deviation of measured phase angle $\arg\{Z\}$) and correct the measured impedance of the UUT. This technique is successfully applied in commercial RCL meters.

However, the gain-phase correction technique is problematic for typical EIS meters. They usually operate only in an auto-ranging mode. Therefore, it is not possible to ensure that a gain-phase error determined with a reference impedance is evaluated at the same internal range as the UUT. In fact, attempting such a correction could even worsen the error. Usually, the standard deviation of a low-impedance measurement (noise) and/or the remaining uncertainty due to the set-up (see previous section) and the UUT, i.e. batteries (see below), are significantly larger than the meter's error. Thus, gain-phase error correction of low-impedances, measured with an EIS meter, is not recommended.

The EIS meter should nevertheless be calibrated with characterized low-impedance standards. First, to check whether the EIS meter operates within its specifications and, secondly, to ensure SI traceability. Standards having a 4TP layout should preferably be used if the meter supports a 4TP scheme. It is also recommended to use standards having a connection scheme and a geometry similar to the UUT.

3.6 Positioning of cells in a temperature-controlled security chamber

A security chamber must be used, the security of level of which is adequate for the cells under test. For more details, the documentation of the cells and the security chamber must be consulted.

Moreover, ensure

- secure stand, using a cell-fixture (if appropriate),
- good air (or inert gas) circulation around the cells to optimise heat dissipation, (an oil bath might even be more appropriate for some kinds of LCTs, needing high temperature homogeneity and stability), and
- electrical insulation from fixture and bearing surface.

3.7 Temperature measurements

A calibrated temperature sensor should be positioned in the test chamber to measure the actual temperature in the chamber during the measurements. Alternatively, the sensor of the test chamber can be used if its measurement error with respect to the mean temperature in the chamber (see 4.9) is regularly quantified and corrected.

Considering measurement accuracy, it is actually not necessary to place temperature sensors on cells. The measurement procedure assumes temperature equilibrium between the batteries and the cells by considering adequate relaxation times between last operation and measurement. However, if the equilibrium condition is doubted due to the specific condition of a set-up (e.g. hampered heat dissipation due to cell positions) it might be necessary to place temperature sensors on some cells and measure the difference between ambient temperature and outer cell temperature.

Moreover, monitoring individual cell temperatures is advisable for safety reasons. Low accuracy sensors can be used for that purpose.

4 Preliminary measurements to specify LCT, impedance and EIS measurement parameters

The subsequent measurements should be conducted before the LCT starts to specify the measurement parameters for the type of cell under investigation. These tests will require several days. However, they only have to be applied once for a given cell type. Given that LCTs usually take several months, the time is well invested, since well-defined parameters prevent test failure and ensure the reliability of the measurement results.

4.1 Limiting voltages

If manufacturer information about limiting voltages U_{cut} and U_{max} is not available for the chosen cycling conditions, it should be verified that the chosen limiting voltages are in a safe operation range when the cycling conditions are applied, i.e. with respect to temperature and charge/discharge currents. To this end, a FC under the chosen cycling conditions and within the chosen voltage limits must be conducted. The charge and discharge voltage must be monitored. The limiting voltages must be in a range that avoids over charging or deep discharging, respectively. Hence, U_{cut} must not be in the range of the steep slope of the SoC-voltage curve, nor may the voltage increase in an accelerated, non-linear manner when approaching U_{max} while CC charging. Otherwise, the voltage limits should be adapted.

Example

The lower end, U_{cut} should be above 3.4V to avoid deep discharge. At the other end, U_{max} should not exceed 4.1 V (it can hardly be seen, however, the voltage starts to increase in a non-linear way around $t=0$).

4.2 Cycling current and temperature limits

Cycling currents and ambient temperatures should be within the limits given by the manufacturer. If this information is not available, 1 C cycling current and 0 °C-40 °C ambient temperature can be considered as safe operation ranges as a rule of thumb. Measuring heat dissipation at the cell surface should be conducted in case of doubt. Surface temperature should not exceed 60 C. LCT tests under stress conditions might require higher currents and higher or lower temperatures, respectively. Obviously, the safety chamber must be designed for destructive testing in this case.

4.3 Capacity measurements

- i. Adjust temperature in the test chamber to the specified measurement temperature t_{meas} .
- ii. Refresh (in case storage time before the capacity measurement has been several months: refresh with 5 FC)
- iii. Adjust SoC 100 %, discharge to SoC 0 % with a specified capacity measurement current i_{meas} and integrate the discharge current to determine the capacity C_{meas} at i_{meas}

$$C_{meas}(i_{meas}) = \int_0^{t \text{ at } U_{cut}} i_{meas}(t') dt' .$$

NOTE: usually, C_{meas} is simply the measured constant current multiplied with the time elapsed until U_{cut} is reached.

- iv. conduct iii with $i_{meas}(n) = n C_{nom}$, $n = \frac{1}{50}, \frac{1}{20}, \frac{1}{10}, \frac{1}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, 1, 2, 5$
- v. specify the optimal capacity measurement current(s) i_c according to the following criteria
 - low noise
 - the measured capacity should ideally show a low dependency on the current
 - cell temperature shouldn't increase significantly above t_{meas}

C_{max} is finally defined as $C_{max} = C_{meas}(i_c)$.

It might be useful to measure capacities during an LCT at two to three specified currents.

Example

Capacity measurements with various currents at 23°C of a commercial 18650 cell. Obviously, there is a significant dependency of the capacity from the measurement current. Here, it has been decided to use $i_c=0.5C$ as a compromise between cell heating, sensitivity of capacity from current and capacity measurement time. Note that high energy cells have shown less sensitivity at lower C rates.

4.4 Initial Quasi OCV measurement

- i. Adjust temperature in the test chamber to the specified measurement temperature t_{meas} .
- ii. Refresh.
- iii. Ensure homogenous temperature by waiting for at least 10 hours.
- iv. Discharge to SoC0 with i_c (as determined in 4.3, if more than one value has been chosen, use the lowest one). Measure cell voltage continuously with a reasonable timely resolution, while charging to SoC 100 % with i_c and, subsequently, discharging to SoC0 with i_c .

4.5 Frequency range for EIS

- i. Adjust temperature in the test chamber to the specified measurement temperature t_{meas} .
- ii. Adjust cell to approximately SoC=50 %.
- iii. Measure a single impedance spectrum in galvanostatic mode, using a provisional AC current i_{ref} . i_{ref} should be
 - in a range of little noise according to the specification of the EIS meter
 - in the expected linearity range of the cell (roughly between C/50 and 1 C)
 - usually C/10 is a good choice

The frequency range should be from 1 mHz to 10 kHz. The step width should be around 10 frequencies per decade.

- iv. Identify the frequency range and steps for the EIS measurements by analyzing the measured spectrum. Obviously, they depend on the cell properties and the impedance features to be investigated. However, as a reasonable rule of thumb they can be determined as follows:

Minimal frequency f_{min} : frequency at which $|Z''(\text{diffusion branch})|$ is double $|Z''(\text{maximum of the largest semicircle})|$. The minimal frequency should not be smaller than 10 mHz to keep measurement time within reasonable limits.

Maximal frequency f_{max} : frequency at which $|Z''(\text{inductive branch})|$ is double $|Z''(\text{maximum of largest semicircle})|$

Step width: There should be enough measuring points to represent the features to be investigated appropriately, i.e. the semicircles; 8-10 steps per frequency decade is often a good compromise between measurement time and resolution.

4.6 AC current for EIS

Small voltage changes effect large current changes at low impedances. Therefore, galvanostatic mode should preferably be chosen for EIS of Li-ion battery cells. Basically, the current must be small enough to generate a linear voltage response and to avoid heating of the cell. On the other hand, it must be sufficiently large to avoid noisy signals. Thus, a trade-off current must be determined.

- i. Adjust temperature in the test chamber to the specified measurement temperature t_{meas} .
- ii. Refresh.
- iii. Adjust approximately SOC = 50 % of the battery cell and wait for at least 10 h.
- iv. Measure EIS in the frequency range and with the provisional current i_{ref} as specified in 4.5.
- v. Conduct EIS measurements with at least 5 currents reasonably distributed in the range $C/50$ to 1 C, wait at least 5 minutes between measurements below $C/2$ and 15 minutes above.

Warning: An impedance measurement can completely charge or discharge a cell if low frequencies and high currents are applied. The operator must avoid overcharging or deep discharge. In fact, the impedance measurement may not change the SOC significantly to be meaningful (stability criterium). Hence, current and/or frequency must be limited such that the change of SOC during an impedance measurement does not exceed 2 %.

- vi. Plot $q_i(f) = \frac{Z'(f,i) - Z'(f,i_{ref})}{Z'(f,i_{ref})}$ against frequency (f) for all currents i chosen in step v in a single plot

- vii. Chose the measurement current according to the following criteria

- q_i must be constant over the whole frequency range within the noise range
- minimum noise
- the mean value \bar{q}_{i2} of the next higher current must be compatible with that of the chosen current \bar{q}_{i1} , i.e. the difference must be smaller than the expanded uncertainty of the difference, using the standard deviation of the mean of the corresponding q_i values as a measure for the uncertainty

$$|\bar{q}_{i2} - \bar{q}_{i1}| < 2\sqrt{\sigma_M^2(q_{i2}) + \sigma_M^2(q_{i1})}^2$$

This requirement should ensure that EIS is measured in the linearity range of the impedances.

² Note that the standard deviation of the mean is $\sigma_M = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}$, with n being the number of q_i values used to calculate \bar{q}_i

Example

q_i -curves for a commercial 18650 NMC cell. The values for q_i decrease for the two highest C-rates at low frequencies, because the system does not respond linear to the excitation. Above 300 Hz the noise increases. Choosing 0.3 A (0.1C) for the excitation amplitude of the 18650-cells has repeatedly caused problems, probably due to long lead wires. Increasing the current amplitude to 0.5 A fixed that issue. Therefore, here it was recommended to use 0.2C ($\approx 0.5A$).

4.7 Relaxation time t_R

To meet the stability criterium for EIS, a battery cell has to achieve an equilibrium condition after the proceeding operation (usually after a refresh cycle). The corresponding relaxation time should be estimated as follows:

- i. Adjust temperature in the test chamber to the specified measurement temperature t_{meas} .
- ii. Refresh.
- iii. Adjust approximately SOC=50 %.
- iv. Start measuring EIS repeatedly with 2-3 frequency steps per decade immediately after SoC has been adjusted. Use the frequency range defined in 4.5 and the measurement current defined in 4.6. Measurement time for a spectrum should not be longer than 15 minutes for high-capacity cells and even smaller for low-capacity batteries. Omit small frequencies in case of need. The EIS-measurements should be repeated for up to 1 h for low-capacity cells and up to 5 h for high-capacity cells (>10 Ah).
- v. Measure a final spectrum after a sufficiently long recess time (e.g. 20h).
- vi. Calculate the change rate of the real parts of the impedances at a given frequency f_g referred to the value after the recess time, this means

$$q_t(Z'(f_g, t_n), t_n) = \frac{\left(\frac{Z'(f_g, t_n) - Z'(f_g, t_{n-1})}{t_n - t_{n-1}} \right)}{Z'(f_g, 20h)}$$

Plot q_t against measurement time t_n for a few selected frequencies f_g representing specific features of the spectrum. The index n indicates the n^{th} EIS measurement. t_n is the corresponding measurement time after the SoC adjustment.

- vii. Likewise, calculate $q_t(Z''(f_g, t_n), t_n)$ using the imaginary parts.

- viii. Relaxation time t_R is given as the time t_n when $Z'(f_g, t_n)$ and $Z''(f_g, t_n)$ have become sufficiently stable. The overall change should not exceed 1%. This means in particular

$$q_t(Z'(f_g, t_R), t_R) \cdot t_m < 1\%$$

t_m is the overall measurement time of a spectrum that corresponds to the frequency range defined in 4.5.

Example

Here, q_t is stable after 150 minutes and has a value of around 0.02/h. Hence, a relaxation time of 150 minutes would be suggested. Under this condition, the overall measurement time should not exceed 30 min, since the change of the impedance during the measurement time is $q_{150min} \cdot 30 \text{ min} \approx 0.01=1\%$.

4.8 Internal resistance R_i

The internal resistance R_i should be measured according to IEC 62660-1. If necessary, measurement currents and times can be reasonably adjusted to the specification of the available measurement equipment and to the parameters determined in this document. Perform the following procedure:

- i. Adjust temperature in the test chamber to the specified measurement temperature t_{meas} .
- ii. Refresh.
- iii. Adjust approximately SoC at which the internal resistance should be measured.
- iv. Wait for t_R after preceding charging or discharging
- v. Discharge with $C_{nom}/3$ for 10 s
- vi. Pause for 10 min
- vii. Charge with $C_{nom}/3$ for 10 s
- viii. Pause for 10 min
- ix. Repeat v - viii for four increasing equally spaced currents up to the maximum current of the measurement device or up to the maximum charge- or discharge current of the cell under test, depending on which of both is smaller.
- x. Plot ΔU over I for each pulse with ΔU being the difference between the voltage at the beginning and the end of one pulse. The slope of the graph gives the internal resistance of the cell.

4.9 Temperature

a) Temperature stability and homogeneity of the test chamber

Position several temperature sensors (uncertainty ≤ 50 mK) in the empty test chamber (at least 5), adjust the temperature of the chamber to the set temperature(s) and measure the temperature distribution(s) after equilibrium conditions have been achieved. Repeat the measurement, with cells inside the chamber, while EIS is measured under the conditions defined above.

This test must be conducted only once, unless the temperature distribution may change significantly for a specific test set-up.

Estimate an uncertainty value for temperature in the safety chamber from the results and note the data file of the LCT.

b) Temperature equilibrium time t_e

Cell temperature has to be in equilibrium with the temperature in the test chamber to perform an impedance measurement. Hence, the time t_e needed to reach equilibrium conditions in the cell after a change of the temperature of the test chamber has to be estimated.

- i. Adjust SOC 50 % of the battery cell type under test.
- ii. Change the temperature in the test chamber according to the expected change(s) during the LCT.
- iii. Measure an impedance spectrum within the defined frequency range and the defined measurement current immediately after you have changed the temperature and start a new measurement every 15 minutes. If the measurement time of a spectrum is more than 15 minutes, reduce the number of (low) frequencies accordingly.
- iv. Estimate t_e from the time elapsed until the change of the impedances is smaller than that after t_R in 4.7.

The uncertainty of the measurement temperature of an impedance measurement must be estimated from the uncertainty of the temperature of the test chamber and uncertainties affecting t_e . Since temperature uncertainty is a mayor contribution to the uncertainty of impedance measurement of Li-ion battery cells it important to quantify this uncertainty.

4.10 Verify causality of impedance spectra

- i. Adjust temperature in test chamber to 23°C
- ii. Refresh.
- iii. Adjust SoC 50 %
- iv. Measure an impedance spectrum of the battery cell under test using the parameters and test conditions defined above.
- v. Conduct a Kramers-Kronig test on the measured spectrum³.

5 Specific requirements for Distributed Relaxation Time Analysis (DRT)

No additional requirements are recommended since DRT is a specific method to analyse measured impedance spectra. However, low noise spectra are preferable since DRT evaluation is particularly sensitive to noisy data.

³ DOI [10.1149/1.2044210](https://doi.org/10.1149/1.2044210).

A test platform is provided at <https://www.iam.kit.edu/et/english/Lin-KK.php>

6 Specific conditions for Nonlinear Frequency Response Analysis (NFRA)

NFRA measurement guide is developed on the basis of the previously defined frequency range and AC current for the EIS measurement. This denotes that those definitions are directly related to EIS definitions if applicable.

6.1 Wiring requirements

Twist the counter electrode and reference electrode wires together and the working electrode and working sense wires respectively. This avoids mutual inductance effects due to interference between the lead wired.

6.2 Frequency range for NFRA

Define the frequency range for the NFRA based on the definition of the EIS frequency range

- Maximum frequency of NFRA, $f_{max,NFRA}$, should be the same as the maximum frequency of the EIS, $f_{max,EIS}$. Further, maximum frequency should allow a separation of harmonic signals from noise. The applicable limit for NFRA depends on the device and is usually below $f_{max,EIS}$. The limit should be provided by the manufacturer of the device (300 Hz for Zahner devices).
- Minimum frequency of NFRA, $f_{min,NFRA}$, is defined at a higher frequency point than EIS measurement, i.e., at 0.1 Hz. This is to avoid the drift of the SoC due to the long measurement time under a larger measurement current during NFR measurement.

6.3 Determination of the measurement current

At least two AC currents with considerable non-linear excitation need to be identified

- Refresh
- Adjust SOC 50 % of the battery cell type under test and wait for at least 10 h
- Conduct reference EIS measurement within the linear range of the impedance by using the measurement current defined for the EIS spectrum, i_{ref} . Use above-defined frequency range, discretized with 10 frequencies per decade above 66 Hz and 5 frequencies per decade below 66 Hz. Further use 3 measure periods (number of sine wave averages) below 66 Hz and 20 measure periods above 66 Hz. Since i_{ref} is in the linear range, NFR spectrum should not yield responses significantly above measurement noise.
- Conduct NFR spectrum measurement with two higher AC currents compared to iii (for example $2 \times i_{ref}$ and $4 \times i_{ref}$. Use above-defined frequency range, discretized with 10 frequencies per decade above 66 Hz and 5 frequencies per decade below 66 Hz. Further use 3 measure periods (number of sine wave averages) below 66 Hz and 20 measure periods above 66 Hz. Wait at least 5 minutes between the measurements.

Warning: Low frequency high amplitude AC current at high SOCs and low temperature cause Li-plating. Hence, this measurement condition must be avoided.

- Repeat step iii. Both impedance spectra measured with i_{ref} may not differ significantly, otherwise iv has to be repeated with a longer relaxation time than 5 minutes.
- Repeat the same experiment from step i to step v for another two battery cells.
- The chosen measurement current for NFRA should satisfy the following criteria:
 - The relative deviation of Y_2 and Y_3 from the repeated experiment is the lowest, i.e., the NFR spectrum measurement with the best repeatability

- b. The excited nonlinear signal arises from the system should be larger than the nonlinear signal arises from the excitation signal, measurement device or noises from the surroundings.
- c. The impedance spectra recorded before (step iii) and after NFR measurement (step v) should not deviate, i.e., the SoC does not drift during the NFR measurement.

7 Typical life cycle test procedure

Preliminary work

- i. Calibrate impedance measurement devices with reference impedances if available.
- ii. Determine and adjust LCT parameters as described in section 4. Make sure the defined measurement conditions comply with the specifications given by the manufacturers of the battery cell and the measurement equipment.
- iii. Mount cells in the test chamber as described in section 3. Do not use cells for the LCT that have already been used to characterise the LCT parameters in step ii.
- iv. Position temperature sensor(s) in the test chamber and the cells.

LCT steps

- v. Adjust temperature in test chamber to the measurement temperature t_{meas} defined for capacity measurements. Wait for time t_e , unless measurement temperature and cycling temperature are the same.
- vi. Refresh
(use 1 C referred to the latest C_{max} measurement).
- vii. Wait for the time t_R .
- viii. Measure the actual capacity C_{max} with the defined measurement current i_c according to section 4.3.iii and the qOCV curve according to 4.4.iv
- ix. Adjust SOC 100 % using the same current as for the capacity measurement.
- x. Adjust cell(s) to the defined measurement SoC using the same current as for the capacity measurement. To this end, discharge the cell(s) with constant i_c for the required amount of time.

NOTE1: Here the SoC is referred to the actual capacity C_{max} which decreases over the run-time of the LCT. Consequently, the discharge time to adjust a specific SoC has to be adapted accordingly.

NOTE2: Ideally, the discharge time should be adjusted for each cell individually, if several cells are measured in parallel on various channels. However, it might be reasonable to calculate a mean discharge time for cells which have been cycled under nominally the same conditions. Potential deviation of the actual SoCs from the set SoC must be considered in the uncertainty budget if necessary.

NOTE3: If other definitions of SoC, e.g. based on C_{nom} , or other procedures for SoC adjustment are used, e.g. cell voltage taken from a qOCV measurement, the procedure has to be adapted accordingly.

- xi. Adjust temperature at which the measurements should be conducted (most often, it will be identical to that of the capacity measurement).
- xii. Wait for the longer one of the periods t_e and t_R .
- xiii. Measure impedance(s). i.e. EIS and/or other quantities (e.g. Coulomb Efficiency, NFRA, internal resistance etc.) of interest.
- xiv. Adjust next measurement temperatures in case of need and repeat xii and xiii (temperature-loop)

- xv. Repeat x to xiv to measure at the next SoCs (SoC-loop).
- xvi. Adjust cycling temperature.
- xvii. Conduct cycling according to the defined number of FCs and according to the defined cycling conditions (C-rate, depth of discharge, recess-time, etc.).
NOTE: If the cycling range is less than 100 % the number of cycles have to be adapted so that the overall charge conversion is equivalent to the defined number of FCs (e.g. cycling between SOC 100% and 50 % would require twice the number of defined FCs).
- xviii. Perform a periodic evaluation of the measurement data. The number of FCs between measurements should be small compared to the expected cycling life, e.g. 1%, time and may be increased later on (5-10%).
- xix. Repeat steps v to xix until the defined end of the LCT.
- xx. Repeat calibration impedance measurement devices with reference impedances.

Automated measurement and cycling procedures might stop during the weekend or vacation time. In this case the temperature in the test chamber should be set to 23 °C and SOC should be adjusted to around 50 %. Restart with a refresh if the procedure continues with a measurement.